

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Performances of composites made from different recycled carbon fibre semi-products

To cite this article: Alexandre Faure *et al* 2023 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2526** 012048

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Performances and Gassing Behavior of Mixed Ti/Nb Oxides As High Potential Li-Ion Anodes](#)
Jean-Francois Colin, Lucienne Buannic, Marlène Chapuis et al.
- [\(Invited\) Tuning the Structure and Property of Electrode Materials of Lithium Battery](#)
Jun-Tao Li, Ling Huang and Shi-Gang Sun
- [Aerodynamic performances of cruise missile flying above local terrain](#)
A Ahmad, M R Saad, A Che Idris et al.

Performances of composites made from different recycled carbon fibre semi-products

Alexandre Faure, Olivier Mantaux, Arnaud Gillet

Univ. Bordeaux, I2M, CNRS, UMR 5295, F-33400 Talence, France

alexandre.faure.1@u-bordeaux.fr

Abstract. Recycled carbon fibres (rCF) were generally chosen for their low price and environmental features. However, performances of composites made of recycled carbon fibres are often too low to compete with lightweight alloys and glass fibre composites materials. As performances of rCF composites depend strongly on the fibres architecture, new semi-products with long and aligned recycled carbon fibres were developed by MANIFICA (Cleansky European Project). The use of long (up to 250mm) and highly aligned recycled fibres now provides rCF composites with excellent mechanical properties.

The purpose of this work is to assess the performances of composites manufactured with these new rCF semi-products. Semi-products with distinct architectures developed by MANIFICA are first presented. Then mechanical performances of composite plates manufactured from the different semi-products are evaluated. Results are finally compared in order to identify the effect of the manufacturing parameters of the semi-products on the final composite properties. This crucial information will allow end-users to select the right semi-product to design recycled carbon fibre composite innovative parts.

Introduction

The MANIFICA project is financed by the European Union as part of Clean Sky 2, to develop a virtuous way to recycle carbon fibres. It includes (i) the collection and the removing of the matrix from the composite waste, (ii) the production of semi-products used to (iii) manufacture aeronautical parts, and (iv) the elaboration of a specific exploitation plan.

MANIFICA aims at setting up an efficient recycling chain for carbon fibres. Its vision is to provide value to recycled carbon fibre, by producing new intelligent semi-products to manufacture high mechanical and environmental performance composites. However, the aeronautic industry requires specific and adapted semi-products to manufacture structural parts. Up to now, current rCF semi-products such as non-woven fabric [1] were not yet able to supply for high performance composites [2]. The University of Bordeaux patented a technology [3], [4] that maintains and controls fibre length and achieves to produce continuous tapes made of highly aligned recycled carbon fibres. This unidirectional tape can be used to produce various semi-products presented in this paper.

Composites made of these different semi-products were tested to evaluate the performance of a new generation of recycled carbon fibre composites.

1. Semi-products developed by MANIFICA

1.1. Tape manufacturing

In this study, carbon fibres used to manufacture semi-products came from standard modulus carbon fibre production offcuts. To ensure the relevance of the results, tapes were produced from the same batch of carbon fibre waste.

Tapes were manufactured, based on the UBx-I2M patented technology [3]. Throughout the reshaping process, carbon fibres are successively, un-woven, aligned, sprayed of a thermoplastic binder (2% of the tape weight) and consolidated by hot air to form an unidirectional tape. In this study two binders were compared: an epoxy powder [5] and a PA6 powder.

The major assets of this process are the alignment and the length of the fibres within the tape [4]. While long fibres provide strength to the composite, fibres alignment provides its stiffness [6].

1.2. Description of the semi-products

Diverse MANIFICA semi-products were investigated here:

- Unidirectional tape (figure 1)
- Unidirectional fabric (figure 2)
- Bidirectional fabric (figure 3)
- Woven-tape bidirectional fabric (figure 4)

Unidirectional fabrics were manufactured by laying tapes side by side and by applying 400°C hot air. The remaining thermoplastic binder sprayed on the rCF tapes was sufficient to create consolidation between the tapes to form the fabric.

Bidirectional fabrics were manufactured by assembling two unidirectional fabrics in perpendicular directions applying either a binder or needle punching [7].

The woven-tape bidirectional fabric was obtained by manually weaving the tape.

Figure 1.
Unidirectional tape

Figure 2.
Unidirectional fabric

Figure 3.
Bidirectional tape

Figure 4. Woven-tape
Bidirectional fabric

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Recycled carbon fibres characteristics

Standard modulus fibres were chosen to manufacture the tape, fibres were chopped using a guillotine at 100-150 mm length. A 32mm width tapes were produced using the alignment process [4].

To manufacture unidirectional fabrics, tapes were assembled then cut into 280x150 mm preforms. Each preform was $700 \text{ g/m}^2 \pm 10\%$.

2.2. Composite plate manufacturing

Composite plates (150x280mm²) were manufactured for each tested configuration.

Composite plates were manufactured by compression moulding on the heating press 5409-000 MIB HYDRO. Four plies of fabrics were placed into a 150x280mm mould and individually impregnated with

Araldite-Aradur LY5052 epoxy resin system by hand [8]. Impregnated fabrics were pressed in the mould at 40°C during 2 hours and 55 minutes at a pressure of 12 bar following the cycle represented on figure 5 to manufacture the composite plates. Once removed from the mould, plates were placed 24h at ambient temperature and then 4 hours at 100°C for post-curing.

Figure 5. Pressing cycle

2.3. Tested composites

One composite plate was manufactured from each MANIFICA semi-product

- Unidirectional composites manufactured with
 - o Epoxy binder unidirectional tape **EUDT** (figure 6)
 - o Epoxy binder unidirectional fabric **EUDF** (figure 7)
 - o PA6 binder unidirectional fabric **PUDF** (figure 8)

Figure 6. EUDT configuration

Figure 7. EUDF configuration

Figure 8. PUDF configuration

- Bidirectional composites were manufactured with
 - o Unidirectional fabrics with 0/90/90/0° configuration **SBDF** (figure 9)
 - o Unidirectional fabrics with 90/0/0/90° configuration **HBDF** (figure 10)
 - o PA6 binded bidirectional fabric **PA6BDF** (figure 11)
 - o Needle punched bidirectional fabric **NPBDF** (figure 12)
 - o Woven-tape bidirectional fabrics **WBDF** (figure 13)

Figure 9. SBDF configuration

Figure 10. HBDF configuration

Figure 11. PA6BDF configuration

Figure 12. NPBDF configuration

Figure 13. WBDF configuration

2.4. Fibre volume fraction of the composite plates

The fibre volume fraction is defined as the fibre volume divided by the whole composite volume as mentioned in equation (1). It mainly depends on the geometric organisation of the fibres and on the manufacturing pressure. The higher the volume fraction the better the mechanical properties of the composite.

The **fibre volume fraction** (V_f) is defined as:

$$V_f = \frac{\rho_m \cdot w_f}{\rho_m \cdot w_f + \rho_f \cdot w_m} \quad (1)$$

V_f is the fibre volume fraction

ρ_m is the density of the matrix in g/cm^3

ρ_f is the density of the carbon fibre g/cm^3

w_f is the fibre weight fraction

w_m is the matrix weight fraction

2.5. Tensile tests

From each plate, 5 tensile samples (250 mm length and 20 mm width) were cut. Tensile tests were operated according to the standard EN 2561 [9]. They were performed on the 3R Syntech machine adapted to the evaluation of tensile modulus and strength. A mechanical extensometer was used in the prescribed range to gauge the Young Modulus.

The **Young modulus** is defined as:

$$E = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

E is the Young modulus (MPa)

$\Delta\sigma$ is the difference in applied tensile stress between two data points (MPa)

$\Delta\varepsilon$ is the longitudinal strain difference between two data points (measured with the extensometers)

The **tensile strength** is defined as:

$$R_{max} = \frac{F_{max}}{S} \quad (3)$$

R_{max} is the maximum tensile strength (MPa)

F_{max} is the maximum tensile force (N)

S is the specimen cross-sectional area (mm^2)

2.6. Interlaminar Shear Strength (ILSS) tests

From each coupon, 6 ILSS samples (20 mm length and 10 mm width) were cut. ILSS tests were performed according to the standard EN 2563 [10]. They were performed on the MTS Alliance RF/100 testing machine.

The apparent interlaminar shear strength τ (MPa), known as ILSS, is defined as:

$$\tau = \frac{3 P_R}{4 b h} \quad (4)$$

P_R is the maximum force at the time of first failure (N)

b is the width of the specimen (mm)

h is the thickness of the specimen (mm)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fibre volume fraction

Figure 14. Fibre volume fraction of composite plates for each MANIFICA semi-product

According to results displayed on figure 14, the fibre volume fraction of unidirectional (UD) composites varies from 59% to 62%. The fibre volume fraction obtained on bidirectional (BD) composites is between 52% and 56%. These very high fibre contents are reached as a result of the very good fibre alignment. This elevates realigned recycled fibre composites to the level of high-performance materials.

3.2. Unidirectional composites

Figure 15. Tensile test results for UD composites

Figure 16. ILSS test results for UD composites

Results on figure 15 and figure 16 tend to indicate that tensile properties are 10% higher and the ILSS is 20% higher using an epoxy binder for UD fabric manufacturing than using PA6 binder. As a matter of fact, the compatibility of the epoxy matrix is better with the epoxy binder than with the PA binder. The latter may be more suitable with a thermoplastic matrix.

However, the performance difference between composite made of UD tapes: EUDT and the composite made of UD fabrics: EUDF is not noticeable. For any unidirectional semi-products used, the tensile strength of the composite is around 620 MPa, the tensile modulus towards 120 GPa and the ILSS is around 50 MPa.

3.3. Bidirectional composites

Figure 17. Tensile test results for BD composites

On figure 17 a clear difference can be spotted between the bidirectional composite made with 0° UD fabrics in the middle (HBDF) and the composite with 0° UD fabrics on the surface (SBDF). While 0° orientation UD fabrics in the middle of the composite provide a 20% better strength, 0° UD fabrics on the surface provide a 20% better stiffness.

According to figure 18, to assemble UD fabrics into BD fabrics, needle punching process (NPBDF) grants a better shear strength than binding the fabrics with a thermoplastic binder (BBDF). Nevertheless, to manufacture bidirectional composites, impregnating plies individually (SBDF), provides better tensile and ILSS properties than assembling plies by needle punching or by binding.

Figure 18. ILSS test results for BD composites

For any BD semi-product used, the tensile strength of the BD composite is between 260 and 400 MPa, the tensile modulus around 46 GPa and the ILSS is between 26 and 40 MPa. This performance is excellent for recycled fibre composites

3.4. Best Performances

To summer up, for each mechanical property, has been listed the reference of the best configuration on table 1.

Table 1. Best configuration for each mechanical property

	Properties	Reference	Best configuration	Highest value
Unidirectional composite	Tensile Strength	EUDT	UD composite made with epoxy UD tape	677 MPa
	Tensile Stiffness	EUDT	UD composite made with epoxy UD tape	134 GPa
	ILSS	EUDP	UD composite made with epoxy UD fabric	58 MPa
Bidirectional composite	Tensile Strength	HBDF	BD composite with 0° UD fabric in the core	400 MPa
	Tensile Stiffness	SBDF	BD composite with 0° UD fabric in the surface	54 GPa
	ILSS	HBDF	BD composite with 0° UD fabric in the core	39 MPa
	ILSS (<i>Binding technology</i>)	NPDF	BD composite with fabrics assembled with needle punching technology	33 MPa

Conclusion

MANIFICA offers a various choice of semi-products made of realigned recycled carbon fibres adapted to the composites industry. In this document the mechanical performances of composites manufactured from MANIFICA semi-products were evaluated. These semi-products were manufactured using different binders, diverse compiling technologies and distinct configurations to provide the best mechanical properties, which is essential for the aeronautic composite industry requirements.

Tensile tests and ILSS tests were performed to assess the mechanical properties of these composites:

- As a result of highly aligned and long recycled carbon fibre within the semi-products, composites manufactured can reach a fibre volume fraction of 60% for unidirectional composites and greater than 50% for bidirectional composites. These results confirm that high performance composites can be manufactured using MANIFICA recycled carbon fibre semi-products.
- The correlation of the results indicated that epoxy binder used to consolidate the tape offers better results than PA6 binder.
- No clear difference of the mechanical properties of the composites can be noticed between laying-up UD fabrics (assembled tapes) or laying-up the tape itself.
- A very specific result was obtained: 0° UD fabrics on the surfaces and 90° fabrics in the core, promotes stiffness rather than strength of the BD MANIFICA composites. Whereas composite manufactured in the opposite way (90° on the surface and 0° in the core) promotes strength rather than stiffness. It confirms that using the same materials in a different configuration offers distinct properties.
- Two compiling technologies to manufacture a bidirectional composite were considered. Needle punching solution offers a higher shear strength compared to the binding solution while a slight drop on the stiffness can be noticed (as some fibres are oriented in the vertical direction).
- Weaving the tape can be identified as a good process to manufacture bidirectional fabrics, however, these materials were hand-made and showed a lot of scattering. A specific machine would be needed to produce this kind of fabric industrially.

All these results bring a good overview of the mechanical performances to be expected using MANIFICA semi-products to manufacture composites. This study points out that recycled carbon fibres can now be used for semi-structural applications.

Bibliography

- [1] S. PICKERING, “Applications for carbon fibre recovered from composites,” *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 139 012005, 2016.
- [2] M. LONGANA, “Recycling of fibre reinforced thermosetting composites,” *Fiber Reinforced Composites*, 2021.
- [3] O. MANTAUX, A. GILLET and M. PEDROS, “Method for unweaving and realigning carbon fibres WO2016066975A1,” 2016.
- [4] A. FAURE, O. MANTAUX and A. GILLET, “New Intelligent Semi-Products based on Recycled Carbon,” *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 1226 012102, 2022.
- [5] “Technical Data Sheet Epoxy EPIKOTE 05390”.
- [6] A. GILLET, O. MANTAUX and G. CAZAURANG, “Characterization of composite materials made from discontinuous carbon fibres within the framework of composite recycling,” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 75, pp. 89-95, 2015.
- [7] X. CHEN, “Three-dimensional needle-punching for composites,” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 85, pp. 12-30, June 2016.
- [8] “Technical Data Sheet Araldite LY-Aradur 5052 epoxy”.
- [9] “NF EN 2561 Plasiques renforcés de fibres de carbone - Stratifiés unidirectionnels Essai de traction parallèlement à la direction des fibres,” 1996.
- [10] “NF EN 2563 Plasiques renforcés de fibres de carbone Stratifiés unidirectionnels Determination de la résistance apparente au cisaillement interlaminaire,” 1997.

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No .887104 The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union

This article reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

